

Thickness control of Snap-Cure Prepregs in Automated Placement Conditions

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CONTENTS

CONTEXT

- **Automated Fibre Placement (AFP)** : Good method for preform production
- **Autoclave manufacturing** : Quality parts, but bottleneck in workflows
- **Technology Need** : Alternative composites manufacturing methods
- **Solutions** : Different materials and heating/curing methods

Autoclave : Three step manufacturing method

CONTEXT

- **Automated Fibre Placement (AFP)** : Good method for preform production
- **Autoclave manufacturing** : Quality parts, but bottleneck in workflows
- **Technology Need** : Alternative composites manufacturing methods
- **Solutions** : Different materials and heating/curing methods

Autoclave : Three step manufacturing method

AFP + VBO : Two step manufacturing method

GOALS

- ◎ **Goal: Enhance the AFP process and enable on-line curing with thermosets (Layer-by-layer manufacturing)**
- ◎ Current manufacturing processes :
 - **3-steps process** : Cold deposition
 - **2-steps process** : Hot deposition
 - **1-step process** : In-situ AFP
- ◎ Approach : Perform compaction tests to characterise materials and process

Desired one-step process

**In-situ consolidation with thermosets:
Curing during the AFP layup step**

CHALLENGES

Feasibility?

Interface ?

Temperature ?

Porosity ?

Degree of Cure ?

Parameters control ?

- **Levers** : AFP Processing parameters
- **Target** : Assess material's suitability
- **Focus** : Control of thickness & voids

Time

Temperature

Pressure

MATERIAL & SETUP

Material : Hexcel M78.1
(Epoxy / Carbon Fibre Prepreg)

Ply Thickness = 0.32 mm

Isothermal Cure Properties by DSC [1]

Temperature	Cure Time (95%)
110°C	≤18min
120°C	≤8min
130°C	≤6min
140°C	≤3min
150°C	≤2min
160°C	≤1.5min

[1] : Hexcel, "HexPly® M78.1 Datasheet", 2020.

Setup : Universal Instron machine,
with custom made heater plates

MATERIAL & SETUP

Material : Hexcel M78.1
(Epoxy / Carbon Fibre Prepreg)

Ply Thickness = 0.32 mm

Cross-ply / Hand lay-up

Setup : Universal Instron machine,
with custom made heater plates

MATERIAL CHALLENGES

- Fibre alignment & stickiness
- Impregnation & flow issues
- Surface defects (channels)

METHODS (1/2) – Bulk samples

Test : Bulk laminates of 5 to 30 plies + Compression at 0.1 MPa (1 bar) for 5 min

Goal : Assess the effect of laminate thickness on final sample thickness & through thickness temperature evolution

METHODS (2/2) – Ply-by-Ply samples

Test : Creation of laminates by compressing each ply at 0.1 MPa (1 bar) for 2.5s

Goal : Assess the process on thickness and porosity evolution

MAIN OBSERVATIONS (1/3)

- M78.1 shows the high reactivity desirable for LBL curing of composite materials.
 - Usable even at low processing temperatures such as 100°C.

Dynamic Complex Viscosity of HexPly® M78.1 @ 5°C/min [1] : Hexcel, "HexPly® M78.1 Datasheet", 2020.

MAIN OBSERVATIONS (2/3)

- M78.1 shows the high reactivity desirable for LBL curing of composite materials.
 - Usable even at low processing temperatures such as 100°C.

Low temperatures (100-130°C)

=

Low viscosity and low cure rate

=

Improvement of the plies bonding

MAIN OBSERVATIONS (3/3)

- M78.1 shows the high reactivity desirable for LBL curing of composite materials.
 - Usable even at low processing temperatures such as 100°C.

High temperatures (140-160°C)

=

Less ply adhesion and dimensional change

=

Generation of defects

CT SCANS (1/4)

Computed Tomography : Feature observation & Porosity measurement

CT SCANS (2/4)

Histogram representation

Porosity observation and measurement

CT SCANS (3/4)

BULK laminate
(160C – 1bar – 5min)

PBP laminate
(160C – 1bar – 2.5s/ply)

CT SCANS (4/4)

Laminates comparison : Bulk vs Ply-by-Ply

BULK laminates

Key Parameters : 10 plies + 1 bar (250N) + 5 min

Cycle time : 5 min (+ layup + debulking = 25 min)

T_{Bulk} (°C) ↑ = Width ≈ Thickness ≈ Defects ≈

Ply-by-Ply laminates

Key Parameters : 10 plies + 1 bar (250N) + 2.5s/ply

Total cycle time : 25 min (handling + compaction)

T_{PBP} (°C) ↑ = Width ↓ Thickness ↑ Defects ↑

FEATURE EVOLUTION

Recommendation : Use medium temperatures. Do not go above 130C for the ply-by-ply process

$T_{\text{Bulk}} (\text{°C})$ ↑ = Width ≈ Thickness ≈ Defects ≈
 $T_{\text{PBP}} (\text{°C})$ ↑ = Width ↓ Thickness ↑ Defects ↑

CURE KINETICS MODEL

Tool developed to optimise compaction parameters (heating rate, hold time, target temperature) & understand in-process property development to achieve target DoC after each compaction cycle.

Outcomes : Ply-by-Ply Cure & Temperature monitoring / Prediction of isothermal times to reach $\alpha^{\text{gel}} = 0.41$

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KEY FINDINGS

🔑 High temperature leads to :

- 🔑 Decreased ply width (**Gel before compaction = less expansion**)
- 🔑 Increased sample thickness (**Less expansion = less squeezing**)
- 🔑 Greater defect generation (**Less squeezing = Less consolidation**)

🔑 Challenges for simultaneous cure-consolidation

- 🔑 The evolving DoC inhibits the consolidation process
- 🔑 Each ply will have a different DoC, processed time, and thickness

CONCLUSIONS

- ③ M78.1 = Material suited for on-line curing via AFP (LBL consolidation)
- ③ Control of thickness and porosity possible with AFP parameters
 - ③ Recommended parameters : 1 bar at 130 °C max.

Next steps

- ③ Use of an AFP rig built in-house at the University of Bristol
- ③ Use of the cure kinetics model to refine the characterisation
- ③ OOA manufacturing of high-quality thermosets composites

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PhD project:
Layer by Layer manufacturing
of complex composites